

What is Future Commons?

Future Commons is a new Research and Mobilization Observatory and Partnership dedicated to the study and promotion of Open Research Practice by individual researchers.

The Partnership is led by an international team of researchers and information professionals that includes some of the most prominent thought-leaders in the Open Access/Open Science movements. Our partner and prospective partner institutions include Libraries and Universities from five continents as well as scholarly societies and consortia dedicated to the mobilisation of Open Research Practices.

How does Future Commons complement other Open Science Initiatives?

Future Commons complements the efforts of other agencies, institutions and consortia by focussing on the cultural change among individual researchers that will be required if Open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) Research Practices are to become the global default.

Most current and previous initiatives in this area have focussed on external, structural and economic issues in Open Research: the economic models, infrastructure and tools, government and institutional policies, and incentive and rewards systems that must change if traditional “closed” research and dissemination practices are to be disrupted.

Future Commons complements this work by focussing on questions of cultural change and individual motivation: What impediments prevent the widespread adoption of Open Practices by the global Research Community? What differences are there in the adoption of Open Research Practices in different disciplines, regions, and generations? How can we understand and facilitate investigator buy-in to Open and FAIR Research Practices? Are there times when Open Research Practices are inappropriate, unethical, or otherwise suboptimal?

We base our work on two key premises about the present state of Scholarly Communication:

1. That transformative change towards Open Research Practices will require sustained and broad popular and practical support from the research world’s scholars, scientists, editors, and publishers, similar to that largely already achieved among its funders, governments, universities, libraries, and policy makers.
2. That developing such popular consensus will require us to learn across and transcend disciplinary, national, regional, sectoral, and other types of fragmentation that traditionally characterise work in this area.

Future Commons provides our partners with a space for developing and coordinating their efforts in Open Research. We intend to supplement and support outreach and mobilisation

efforts by our Partner institutions and provide support for research, mobilisation, and cross-silo networking efforts focussed on promoting Open Research Practice to individual researchers.

How will Future Commons be funded?

Future Commons is in the process of developing an application to the Canadian Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) Partnership Programme for 6 year/\$2.5 million (CAD) in funding. This funding will support both the development of a virtual observatory and three main streams of activity: Networking and Facilitation, Incubation, and Mobilisation (A previous \$200,000 grant from SSHRC's Partnership Development Grant Programme helped support the initial formation of the Partnership and funded the development of activities such as the Force11 Scholarly Communication Institute).

Who are the current partners?

The following institutions have joined or are actively pursuing association with **Future Commons**: Curtin University (Australia); Elizade University (Nigeria); Force11; Indian Institute of Technology, Indore; NYU (USA); SPARC; UCLA (USA); Université de Montréal (Canada); University of Lethbridge (Canada); Utrecht University (Netherlands).

How does my Institution, Group, or Project join Future Commons?

Future Commons welcomes expressions of interest from institutions and organisations active in the development or promotion of Open Research Practices. Partners join **Future Commons** through a negotiated letter of agreement indicating how participation fits with their current or planned activities and strategic priorities in Open Research and the resources and activities they bring to the network. Partners participate in the overall design and governance of the Partnership and benefit from opportunities to leverage their contributions through joint action and access to supplementary funding.

Can I join as an individual?

Individuals participate in **Future Commons** through their institutions, by joining the current leadership team, or, assuming the project is funded, participating in its activities. Depending on the timing and level of this participation, individuals may be required to register with SSHRC and provide a CV.

Contact

For further details or to inquire about joining **Future Commons**, please contact the project director

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Basic Information on the SSHRC Partnership Programme¹

The SSHRC Partnership Grant competition is unusual in several respects:

1. It is awarded to institutions rather than individuals. The grant is prepared by a director on behalf of a lead institution (in this case the University of Lethbridge).
2. It requires participation by other institutional partners (Canadian or International)
3. Non-Canadian individuals and institutions can play a more central role than in other SSHRC funding programmes: unlike other SSHRC grants, non-resident individuals may be listed as “Co-applicants” (normally they may only be collaborators); the grant can pay direct research costs for non-Canadian resident co-applicants and institutions.
4. The competition requires applicants to secure the equivalent of an additional 35% of the amount requested from SSHRC in cash or in-kind “contributions” from its partners.

The competition is run in two stages:

1. Stage 1 (formerly Letter of Intent): Prospective Partnerships submit a reduced application indicating their proposed programme of activity and current and proposed partners (Due Feb 15, 2019). At this stage only broad budget costs are required and partnerships may still be prospective. Successful applicants at this stage are awarded \$20k (CAD) to prepare a full application for Stage 2.
2. Stage 2: Applicants who were successful at Stage 1 are invited to submit a full application detailing their programme of activity, partners, and a detailed budget (November 30, 2019).

Recently, the success rate for the competition as a whole has been about 25% of Stage 1 applicants. SSHRC has indicated that more money is available in 2019-2020.

Leveraging

In order to be eligible for funding, proposals must demonstrate that they have been able to raise the equivalent of an additional 35% of the amount requested from SSHRC. This can be in cash or kind and may take the form of new funds or funds already committed to activities planned for the funding period.

Partners are not required to make a contribution as a condition of joining the grant, though the definition of “contribution” is such that most already are through their support of associated activities and research. As a result, most applications to the programme have far more than the equivalent of 35% in matching contributions.

The best partners for this grant are institutions that are already active or planning to become active in Open Research since those activities can be counted as a contribution. Contact the director for more details.

¹ Please note: This is an unofficial summary. For official details please see the SSHRC website.